

A TWO-DIMENSIONAL FINITE ELEMENT PROCESSING MODEL FOR FRP COMPOSITE COMPONENTS

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ABSTRACT

A major obstacle to realizing the full potential of composite structures in commercial applications is cost-effective manufacturing. To achieve this objective, it is desirable that a science-based approach to manufacturing be developed. Past efforts have demonstrated the usefulness of process modelling as a predictive tool for simple structures and boundary conditions. In this work, a comprehensive 2-D finite element processing model for composites has been developed which extends previous modelling work, addressing important issues such as complex geometries, effects of process tooling, and simulation of automated autoclave control.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past two decades, a large number of models for processing of polymeric composite materials have been developed [e.g. 1-8] and their usefulness has become increasingly apparent. Some models have focused largely on a single phenomenon such as heat transfer and resin reaction kinetics [e.g. 4,6,7], resin flow [e.g. 2], or stress development [e.g. 8,9] while others have been more broad in scope, including analyses of a number of phenomena in a single model [e.g. 1,3,5].

The processing of composite materials may be examined on a number of size scales ranging from the level of individual fibres and the surrounding matrix (micromechanics) to a 'global discretization' level at which an entire large-scale structure is analysed (Fig. 1). Between these extremes is the 'local discretization' level at which a structure of intermediate size and complexity can be modelled while employing elements small enough to adequately analyse the most important process phenomena. By examining typical sub-components of a larger structure, the predictions of such model can be used in 'global discretization' level models to predict the processing behavior of even the largest composite components. Current processing models are valuable for predictions on simple structures. However, these models cannot analyse all the major processing phenomena in components of appreciable complexity.

This paper presents a two-dimensional finite element model developed specifically to analyse industrial autoclave processing of composite structures of intermediate size and complexity. We first outline the model assumptions, the theoretical background and solution strategies for the various program modules. A case study is then presented to demonstrate the capabilities and features of the model.

PROCESS MODEL DEVELOPMENT

A modular approach is employed for the overall program structure, similar to that described by Loos and Springer [1]. As illustrated in Fig. 2, the main body of the program consists of a series of 'modules', each responsible for performing a single task such as calculating resin flow (the 'flow-compaction' module) or development of internal stresses (the 'stress-deformation' module). The various modules are called as needed by a controlling routine as the solution marches forward in time. At the beginning of each time step, an 'autoclave controller' module, simulating automated autoclave control, updates all process variables including the autoclave air temperature, the autoclave pressure and the vacuum bag pressure. A central database containing a description of the modelled components (i.e. composite, tool, inserts, etc.) is updated by each solution module as it is called.

MODEL DESCRIPTION

The focus of the present model is on the analysis of composites processing at the 'local discretization' level illustrated in Fig. 1. Using this model, the cross-section of a complete sub-structure is discretized into 2-D quadrilateral elements. In addition to uncured composite materials, other structural components such as pre-cured frames or honeycomb inserts as well as process tooling may be directly included in the model. The governing equations describing the various processing phenomena are solved using finite element techniques. Performing the analysis on only a 2-D section is believed to be adequate for most composite structures as at least one dimension is usually much larger than the other two. Gradients in this third direction are correspondingly small and can safely be ignored.

Thermochemical module

The thermochemical module is responsible for calculation of the distribution of component temperature and the degree of resin chemical advancement (degree of cure). This module consists of a combination of analyses for heat transfer and resin reaction kinetics. The governing equation for heat transfer in the 2-D cartesian co-ordinates (x, z) used is:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho C_p T) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k_x \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(k_z \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) + \rho_R \dot{H} \quad (1)$$

where ρ_R is the resin density, \dot{H} is the specific rate of heat generation of the resin's exothermic reaction, ρ and C_p are the composite density and specific heat respectively, and k_x and k_z are the thermal conductivities. The composite thermophysical properties (ρ , C_p , k_x , and k_z) used in Eqn. (1) are calculated from the local fibre volume fraction (V_f), and instantaneous resin and fibre properties.

The rate of heat generation in Eqn. (1) can be determined from:

$$\dot{H} = \frac{d\alpha}{dt} H_R \quad (2)$$

where $d\alpha/dt$ is designated as the cure rate and H_R is the total amount of heat generated during a complete resin reaction. A large number of different mechanistic, empirical, and semi-empirical models have been proposed for predicting the cure rate of various resin systems [e.g. 1,4,7]. Six of the most widely used models are currently available in this module, and others can easily be added as needed.

The boundary conditions that may be used with the thermochemical module include: specified boundary temperature, convective heat transfer or no heat transfer (adiabatic). Different conditions (e.g. different heat transfer coefficients) can be applied to each element as desired. Either explicit or implicit techniques may be chosen to solve the heat transfer (Eqn. 1) and cure rate equations. Using either technique, these two equations are uncoupled during each solution time-step. This approach facilitates a simplified and modular solution procedure and is sufficiently accurate if small time steps are used.

Flow-Compaction module

The flow-compaction module is solved only for the curing composite. The resin viscosity, the resin pressure, composite deformation and local composite fibre volume fraction are updated at each time step. The composite material is assumed to be an elastic, deformable, porous medium in which the resin flows relative to the fibre bed according to Darcy's law. The flow-compaction module solves two governing equations: the stress equilibrium and the resin continuity equations. Using the effective stress formulation, the stress equilibrium in 2-D cartesian coordinates is:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{xz}}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} + F_x = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}_z}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{xz}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} + F_z = 0 \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_x$, $\bar{\sigma}_z$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{xz}$ are the effective stresses, P is the resin pressure and F_x and F_z are the body forces. The continuity equation for the resin is given by:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_x + \dot{\epsilon}_z = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{K_x}{\mu} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{K_z}{\mu} \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} \right) \quad (5)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}_x$ and $\dot{\epsilon}_z$ are the composite strain rates, K_x and K_z are the fibre bed permeabilities and μ is the resin viscosity. The resin viscosity is a function of its temperature and degree of cure and can be obtained from any number of empirical models [e.g. 1,7]. The fibre bed compaction behavior and the fibre bed permeability are functions of the fibre volume fraction, V_f . Both are calculated using empirical or analytical models available from the literature [2,10,11].

The boundary conditions that may be simulated with the flow-compaction module are: autoclave pressure, impermeability or permeability with prescribed bag pressure, no displacement or no normal displacement (tangent sliding condition). The governing equations (eqns. 4 and 5) are coupled during individual time-steps of the transient solution. A Newton-Raphson iterative procedure is used to solve the resulting non-linear system of equations.

Stress-Deformation module

The stress-deformation module models the development of internal stresses and deformations within a component throughout the processing cycle. Process-induced stresses can significantly affect both the ultimate strength of composite structures and their fatigue life. Furthermore, these stresses can induce both in-plane dimensional changes and structural warpage well beyond acceptable tolerance limits.

The current model incorporates analyses of all five major sources of process-induced stress identified from the literature. These are:

- 1) Anisotropic ply thermal expansion
- 2) Anisotropic resin cure shrinkage
- 3) Internal gradients in temperature and resin degree of cure

- 4) Uneven resin flow
- 5) Process tooling effects (anisotropic boundary conditions and boundary friction).

Currently, a hardening linear elastic material model is used to describe the behavior of the curing resin. At the start of each module time step, ply mechanical properties are determined from micromechanics models using the local fibre volume fraction (V_f) and fibre and resin properties calculated from the local temperature and degree of cure.

For the finite element solution, four-noded, plane strain, isoparametric elements are employed. To reduce solution time to manageable levels, each element typically includes several plies throughout its thickness. A combined trapezoidal/Gaussian integration rule is used to smear the ply properties and strains to obtain equivalent element stiffnesses and nodal displacements.

Autoclave controller module

An important concept used in the present process modelling approach is that of the 'virtual autoclave'. Virtual sensors can be placed at element nodes and are monitored just as thermocouples would in a real part. These 'measured' temperatures are used by controller algorithms based on those used in actual autoclaves to set the air temperature and autoclave pressure for the next model time step. Also, other autoclave characteristics may be simulated, such as maximum heating rates (based on maximum heater capacity and part/autoclave thermal mass) and the boundary heat transfer coefficient (as a function of autoclave temperature and pressure). Incorporating into the model the characteristics of autoclave controllers extends its potential application from purely academic studies to a tool that may be applied directly to processing problems encountered in realistic industrial environments.

CASE STUDY

To demonstrate the capabilities of the present model, a simulation of the processing cycle of a composite angle is presented (Fig. 3). A 36 ply quasi-isotropic non-symmetric $[0/+45/-45/90]_9$ layup is used for the component, which is processed on a solid, square male tool. The composite material properties used are typical of a second generation carbon-fibre toughened-epoxy resin material. The autoclave air pressure and temperature are applied according to a typical production cure cycle (Fig. 3). A convection boundary condition is simulated on all boundaries. A bleeder maintained at the bag vacuum pressure (Fig. 3) was used as the resin flow boundary condition. Perfect bonding between the laminate and the tool is assumed.

RESULTS

An important aspect of the present model is its ability to model complex shapes with realistic boundary conditions. Figure 4 shows model predictions of part temperature and resin degree of cure demonstrating the effect of process tooling. Neglecting the tool leads to both a temperature overshoot and a shorter cure cycle. Including an aluminum tool in the simulation increases the cycle time by about 90 minutes and eliminates the temperature overshoot. Using a different tool material such as invar further lengthens the cure cycle.

The resin flow during processing will influence the laminate local dimensions, particularly with complex shapes. As shown in Figure 5, the present model can predict the local thickness variation due to resin flow. As the resin viscosity decreases, flow of the resin out of and within the part leads to uneven laminate thickness. For example, for the case studied, the thickness change in the flat section of the laminate is greater than at the corner.

The final part shape is predicted by the stress-deformation module as shown in Figure 6. The local fibre volume fraction is non-uniform ranging from 60.7% at the corner to 64.0% at the angle flat section. Such non-uniformity affects most laminate properties and must be considered for accurate prediction of the part final shape.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

A 2-D finite element process model for composites has been developed which includes the following effects:

- complex geometries
- analysis of heat transfer, cure kinetics, resin flow, residual stresses
- realistic boundary condition modelling
- industrial autoclave controller simulation

A case study has been presented to demonstrate the capabilities of the current model. Future model development will improve capabilities in a number of areas such as a more realistic description of the tool-laminate interface.

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Figure 1 Range of scales of interest in modelling the processing of composite structures.

Figure 2 Process model structure.

Figure 3 Case study- quasi-isotropic 36 ply layup angle on a male tool.

Figure 4 Tool effect on temperature and cure predictions for a 36 ply quasi-isotropic layup angle.

Figure 5 Thickness change and viscosity prediction for a 36 ply quasi-isotropic layup angle moulded on an aluminum tool.

Figure 6 Warpage (spring-in angle: 1.1°) and local fibre volume fraction prediction for a 36 ply quasi-isotropic layup angle moulded on an aluminum tool.